

1. ACM Digital Library

(Title:(("program repair" OR "code repair" OR (("automated" OR "automatic" OR "automatically") AND ("program" OR "code" OR "bugs" OR "vulnerabilities" OR "software" OR "warnings") AND ("repair" OR "repairing" OR "repairs" OR "fix" OR "fixes" OR "fixing"))) OR "patch generation") OR Keyword:(("automated program repair" OR "automatic program repair" OR "program repair" OR "vulnerability repair" OR "bug repair" OR "automated repair" OR "automatic repair" OR "patch generation")) AND AllField:(("static code analysis" OR "static analysis" OR "static analyzer" OR "static program analysis" OR "source code analysis"))

2. IEEE Xplore Digital Library

("Document Title":("program repair" OR "code repair" OR ("Document Title":("automat*" AND ("Document Title":("program" OR "code" OR "warnings" OR "bugs" OR "vulnerabilities" OR "software") AND ("Document Title":("repair*" OR "Document Title":("fix*")) OR "Document Title":("patch generation" OR "Author Keywords":("automated program repair" OR "Author Keywords":("automatic program repair" OR "Author Keywords":("program repair" OR "Author Keywords":("vulnerability repair" OR "Author Keywords":("bug repair" OR "Author Keywords":("automated repair" OR "Author Keywords":("automatic repair" OR "Author Keywords":("patch generation")) AND ("Full Text .AND. Metadata":("static code analysis" OR "Full Text .AND. Metadata":("static analysis" OR "Full Text .AND. Metadata":("static analyzer" OR "Full Text .AND. Metadata":("static program analysis" OR "Full Text .AND. Metadata":("source code analysis"))

3. Scopus

(TITLE("program repair" OR "code repair" OR (("automated" OR "automatic" OR "automatically") AND ("program" OR "code" OR "warnings" OR "bugs" OR "vulnerabilities" OR "software") AND ("repair" OR "repairing" OR "repairs" OR "fix" OR "fixes" OR "fixing"))) OR "patch generation") OR KEY("automated program repair" OR "automatic program repair" OR "program repair" OR "vulnerability repair" OR "bug repair" OR "automated repair" OR "automatic repair" OR "patch generation")) AND ALL("static code analysis" OR "static analysis" OR "static analyzer" OR "static program analysis" OR "source code analysis") AND PUBYEAR > 2008 AND PUBYEAR < 2026

4. Springer

Query 1

Title :

"program repair" OR "code repair" OR (("automated" OR "automatic" OR "automatically") AND ("program" OR "code" OR "bugs" OR "vulnerabilities" OR "software" OR "warnings") AND ("repair" OR "repairing" OR "repairs" OR "fix" OR "fixes" OR "fixing"))) OR "patch generation"

Keywords (All words in Springer's context) :

"static code analysis" OR "static analysis" OR "static analyzer" OR "static program analysis" OR "source code analysis"

Query 2

Keywords (All words in Springer's context) :

("static code analysis" OR "static analysis" OR "static analyzer" OR "static program analysis" OR "source code analysis") AND ("automated program repair" OR "automatic program repair" OR "program repair" OR "vulnerability repair" OR "bug repair" OR "automated repair" OR "automatic repair" OR "patch generation")

5. Wiley Interscience

Query 1

Title :

"program repair" OR "code repair" OR (("automated" OR "automatic" OR "automatically") AND ("program" OR "code" OR "bugs" OR "vulnerabilities" OR "software" OR "warnings") AND ("repair" OR "repairing" OR "repairs" OR "fix" OR "fixes" OR "fixing")) OR "patch generation"

Anywhere :

"static code analysis" OR "static analysis" OR "static analyzer" OR "static program analysis" OR "source code analysis"

Query 2

Anywhere :

"static code analysis" OR "static analysis" OR "static analyzer" OR "static program analysis" OR "source code analysis"

Keywords :

"automated program repair" OR "automatic program repair" OR "program repair" OR "vulnerability repair" OR "bug repair" OR "automated repair" OR "automatic repair" OR "patch generation"

6. Science Direct

This has limited advanced search capabilities (only 8 boolean operators are permitted in the query). We can break the query and aggregate the results separately.

[Q1]Title - "program repair" OR "code repair" OR (("automated" OR "automatic" OR "automatically") AND ("program" OR "code" OR "bugs" OR "vulnerabilities" OR "software" OR "warnings") AND ("repair" OR "repairing" OR "repairs" OR "fix" OR "fixes" OR "fixing")) OR "patch generation"

OR

[Q2]Key Words/Title/Abstract - "automated program repair" OR "automatic program repair" OR "program repair" OR "vulnerability repair" OR "bug repair" OR "automated repair" OR "automatic repair" OR "patch generation"

[Q3]All Fields - "static code analysis" OR "static analysis" OR "static analyzer" OR "static program analysis" OR "source code analysis"

Complete Query = (Q1 OR Q2) AND Q3
= (Q1 AND Q3) OR (Q3 AND Q2)

Since the title query contains more than eight boolean operators, it is divided as follows.

[T1]Title - "program repair" OR "code repair" OR "patch generation"

[T2]Title - ("automated" OR "automatic" OR "automatically") AND ("program" OR "code" OR "bugs") AND ("repair" OR "repairing" OR "repairs")

[T3]Title - ("automated" OR "automatic" OR "automatically") AND ("vulnerabilities" OR "software" OR "warnings") AND ("repair" OR "repairing" OR "repairs")

[T4]Title - ("automated" OR "automatic" OR "automatically") AND ("program" OR "code" OR "bugs") AND ("fix" OR "fixes" OR "fixing")

[T5]Title - ("automated" OR "automatic" OR "automatically") AND ("vulnerabilities" OR "software" OR "warnings") AND ("fix" OR "fixes" OR "fixing")

Complete Query = ((T1 OR T2 OR T3 OR T4 OR T5) AND Q3) OR (Q3 AND Q2)
= **(T1 AND Q3) OR (T2 AND Q3) OR (T3 AND Q3) OR (T4 AND Q3) OR (T5 AND Q3) OR (Q3 AND Q2)**